

THE RELATIVE DORMANCY OF NEWLY INTRODUCED PEACH CULTIVARS CHARACTERISTIC**Asadova Basti,***Ph.d.,**Azerbaijan Pedagogical University***Faiqa Aslanova***PhD student,**Baku State University***Abstract**

The rapid growth of the world's population increases the demand for the effective functioning of the agricultural sector in the era of global climate change, which implies the production of higher agricultural products with less resources. The agrarian economy of our republic is constantly developing with the application of new technologies. The development of the non-oil sector, the production of export-oriented products, and the reduction of dependence on imports are among the priorities for ensuring the sustainable development of the economy. The natural climatic conditions of our country allow the formation of multi-field and productive agriculture as a whole. Our republic, having an ancient agricultural culture, has favorable soil and climate conditions for the development of various fields of agriculture, and this has been confirmed in various sources.

Keywords: global climate change, peach plant, relative calmness, vegetation period

As in all fruit plants, the development of the peach plant is characterized by 2 periods: relative rest and vegetation period.

In deciduous trees and shrubs, the phase of relative dormancy begins with leaf shedding and lasts until the period of bud swelling. In these plants, it occurs as a result of the weakening of the intensity of physiological-biochemical processes in the cell protoplasm and changes in metabolism. Although the plant retains its appearance during the dormant period, flowers, leaves, pods and fruits do not form on it. However, although many physiological processes such as respiration, transpiration and metabolism continue, the speed of these processes is slow. A period of relative dormancy is observed in both tissues and shoots. Thus, in the peach plant, shortly after fertilization, the embryo develops and forms through the process of division, and the plant again transitions to the dormant period. It can be concluded that the phase of relative rest in plant ontogeny is first observed in the zygote. Physiologists divide the period of relative dormancy in fruit and berry plants into 3 half-periods: the beginning of the period of relative dormancy, natural (physiological, organic, or deep) and forced relative dormancy. At this stage, the intensity of metabolism weakens, the growth of meristem tissues in the top shoot stops, and the accumulation of starch in the tissues reaches its maximum, while the activity of the cambium starts from the tip of the umbrella, gradually from top to bottom, and finally stops at the root throat. Plants need a temperature of 0°C, and most fruit and berry plants need a temperature of +5...+7°C to pass the natural rest period [1,3-14].

The different climatic conditions of the autumn season, which lead to the weakening of senescence, change the resorption time and efficiency compared to normal senescence, which leads to higher

concentrations in dormant organs [1-12,24,25].

As mentioned by many authors [2-9], the basis of the period of relative rest is the stop of division in the meristem tissues of the plant and

Along with the changes in metabolism, it is the weakening of physiological processes during the development of vegetative organs. According to observations, a period of relative rest begins when the air temperature drops below + 10°C, and this period ends when the temperature rises in early spring and the shoots begin to develop. In the autumn rainy years, excess irrigation and excessive use of nitrogenous fertilizers lead to a long period of relative rest, and if drought is observed, excessive use of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers causes this phase to be shortened.

According to the observations of T.A. Latsko, the damage of stone fruit plants from winter frosts in the period of relative silence is 7.3% in cherry, 19.7% in plum, 80.5% in peach and 95.7% in apricot [4-12]. In the peach varieties that we observed, no damage from winter frosts was observed during the phase of relative rest.

In the life of plants, the stage of relative calm is of special importance. Because at this stage, there are favorable conditions for the implementation of agrotechnical measures (fertilizing, shaping and pruning, moving the plant from one area to another, fighting against diseases and pests, etc.) that play an important role in the life of the plant.

In the research years (2021-2023), the period of relative rest depending on the agrobiological characteristics of the newly introduced peach varieties, the soil-climate conditions of the area and the air temperature conditions for each year in the conditions of the Guba-Khachmaz economic region was studied, and the results of the study are shown in table 1.

Table 1.

Newly introduced peach varieties a phase of relative calm

Sortlar	2021		2022		2023	
	Başlaması	Sonu	Başlaması	Sonu	Başlaması	Sonu
Fə dai (n)	16.XI	28.III	19.XI	01.IV	06.XI	20.III
Meloks26	14.XI	30.III	18.XI	02.IV	10.XI	22.III
Netiks25	10.XI	28.III	14.XI	01.IV	08.XI	20.III
Rediks 25	10.XI	24.III	14.XI	26.III	06.XI	16.III
Maliks25	10.XI	27.III	14.XI	30.III	08.XI	20.III
Rediks27	16.XI	31.III	20.XI	02.IV	11.XI	22.III
Netiks28	18.XI	31.III	20.XI	02.IV	12.XI	22.III
Netiks30	18.XI	28.III	20.XI	01.IV	09.XI	21.III
Quayoks30	18.XI	24.III	13.XI	26.III	10.XI	16.III
Rediks30	17.XI	27.III	18.XI	30.III	10.XI	20.III
Maliks145	15.XI	25.III	28.XI	28.III	08.XI	18.III
Meloks31	20.XI	30.III	24.XI	03.IV	13.XI	23.III
Meloks37	20.XI	02.IV	25.XI	04.IV	15.XI	25.III
Rediks2-110	16.XI	27.III	20.XI	30.III	12.XI	22.III
Netiks34	16.XI	28.III	20.XI	01.IV	08.XI	20.III
Maliks36	20.XI	30.III	24.XI	03.IV	13.XI	23.III
Quayoks-35	18.XI	28.III	22.XI	01.IV	07.XI	20.III
Qarteyro	10.XI	22.III	12.XI	25.III	04.XI	15.III
Qardeta	08.XI	20.III	09.XI	20.III	08.XI	12.III

During the research years, the relative dormancy phase lasted 112-142 days for varieties, 123-135 days on average. This period is the same (129 days) in Netix 28, Netix 34, Redix 2-110 varieties as compared to the control variety (Fedai), Melox 26, Netix 25, Redix 25, Maliks 25, Redix 27 and Garteiro varieties (130-135 days), long, while in other varieties it lasted relatively short (123-128 days). The duration of the relative rest period was the least in Maliks 145 (123 days) and the longest in Netix 25 (135 days) compared to the control (Fedai) and other research varieties.

References

- Melgar, J.C., Lawrence, B.T. Variable Fall Climate Influences Nutrient Resorption and Reserve Storage in Young Peach Trees // *Frontiers in Plant Science*, - 2018. № 9:1819, - p.1-11.
- Hasanov, Z.M. Fruit growing / Z.M. Hasanov, C.M. Aliyev. - Baku: MBM, - 2011. - 520 p.
- Aliyev, C.M. Fruit growing / C.M. Aliyev. - Baku: Maarif, - 1974. - 303 p.Лацко, Т.А.
- Оценка зимостойкости сортов и форм персика при экстремальных температурах в степной зоне Крыма // -Ялта: Сборник научных трудов ГНБС, - 2015. Том 140, -с. 34-46.
- Асадова, Б. Г. (2020). Роль фермента глюкозы-6-фосфатдегидрогеназы в адаптации растений к соленым условиям. *Spirit Time*, (1-1), 6-9.
- Huseynova, N., & Asadova, B. (2024). Study of the Genome Diversity of *Cornus L.* and *Mespilus L.* Cultivated in the Northern Regions of Azerbaijan.
- Asadova, B. (2023). Механизм устойчивости растений гороха к Na₂SO₄. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 9(2).
- Basti, A. (2023). EFFECTS OF NaCl SALT STRESS ON BIOMETRIC PARAMETERS IN PISUM VARIETIES. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 9(4), 125-130.
- Mirzoyeva, B. A. (2017). Influence of Na Salt Solutions on the Germination, Development and Dynamics of the Activity of Nadp-Enzyme of Barley Seeds. *International Journal of Sciences*, 6(04), 42-47.
- Asadova, B., & Sarhadova, Z. (2024). ECONOMIC INDICATORS AND PRODUCTIVITY OF NEWLY INTRODUCED PEACH VARIETIES TO AZERBAIJAN. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (88).
- Гусейнова, Н. Т., & Асадова, Б. К. (2024). ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ГЕНОМНОГО РАЗНООБРАЗИЯ КИЗИЛА И МУШМУЛЫ, ВОЗДЕЛЫВАЕМЫХ В СЕВЕРНЫХ РАЙОНАХ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА. <https://www.bulletennauki.ru>, 79.
- Shahryari, R., Gurbanov, E., Gadimov, A., & Hassanpanah, D. (2008). Tolerance of 42 bread wheat genotypes to drought stress after anthesis. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences: PJBS*, 11(10), 1330-1335.
- Babaev, M. P., Gurbanov, E. A., & Ramazanova, F. M. (2015). Main types of soil degradation in the Kura-Aras Lowland of Azerbaijan. *Eurasian soil science*, 48, 445-456.
- Hassanpanah, D., Gurbanov, E., Gadimov, A., & Shahriari, R. (2008). Determination of yield stability in advanced potato cultivars as affected by water deficit and potassium humate in Ardabil region, Iran. *Pakistan journal of biological sciences: PJBS*, 11(10), 1354-1359.
- Shahryari, R., Gadimov, A., Gurbanov, E., & Valizade, M. (2009). Application of potassium humate in wheat for organic agriculture in Iran. *As. J. Food Ag-Ind*, 164-168.
- Gurbanov, E. M. (2009). Systematics of higher plants. Baku: BGU, 429.
- Shahryari, R., Gurbanov, E., Gadimov, A., & Hassanpanah, D. (2008, September). In vitro effect of potassium humate on terminal drought tolerant bread

wheat. In Proceedings of the 14th meeting of International Humic Substances Society.

18. Duniyaliyev, S., Mustafayev, Z., Aslanova, F., & Gatamov, K. (2021). Agrobiologicheskaya kharakteristika razlichnykh sortov kukuruzy i ikh rol' v selektsii na vlazhnykh pochvakh Azerbaydjana. Bulletin of Science and Practice, 7(6).

19. Youssef, N. A., Gurbanov, E. M., Hacıyeva, S. R., Mammedova, A. O., & Khalilov, R. I. (2013). Antioxidant enzymes, fluctuating asymmetry and morphological changes of urban trees as an ecological indicator of heavy metal stress. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Health Care, 3(1), 1-18.

20. Hassanpanah, D., Gurbanov, E., Gadimov, A., & Shahriari, R. (2008). Shortening transplantation periods of potato plantlets by use of potassium humate and kadostim and their effects on mini-tuber production. Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences: PJBS, 11(10), 1370-1374.

21. Aslanova, S. (2023). New Locations of Some Plant Species in the Mountain Part of Yardimli, Lerik and Astara Districts (Azerbaijan). Bulletin of Science and Practice.

22. Gurbanov, E., & Aslanova, S. (2024). AVERAGE ANNUAL PRODUCTIVITY OF THE

THYMUSETA-VİCAETUM-FESTUCOSUM FORMATION, DISTRIBUTED IN SUMMER PASTURE FIELD NO. 8" TURKESOBA"(AZERBAIJAN). Norwegian Journal of Development of the International Science, 126.

23. Aslanova, S. (2021). Effect of Ecological Conditions on Change of Some Morphological Characteristics and Yield of Corn Hybrids. Bulletin of Science and Practice.

24. Elshad, K., Aslanova, S., & Aslanova, F. (2024). BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES. Annali d'Italia №, 58, 3.

25. Yusifova, A., Asadova, B., & Aslanova, S. (2024). SPECIES COMPOSITION AND RESOURCES OF CULTIVATED AND WILD FORAGE PLANTS IN AZERBAIJAN. German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft, (84).

26. Duniyaliyev, S., Mustafayev, Z., Aslanova, F., & Gatamov, K. (2021). Agrobiological Characteristics of Different Varieties of Corn and Their Role in Breeding on Wet Soils in Azerbaijan. Bulletin of Science and Practice.